

TABLE I

Myristic acids.	M.P.	M.P. (isomeric acids)
α -Ethyl-	61°	62°
α -Butyl ⁿ -	68°	
α -Butyl ⁱ -	66°	69°
α -Butyl ^t -	62°	
α -Phenyl-	73°	75.3°

TABLE II

pH of the soap solutions at 33°.

Conc.	Ethyl-		Butyl ⁿ -		Butyl ⁱ -		Butyl ^t -		Phenyl-	
	pH.	%Hydrolysed.	pH.	%Hydrolysed.	pH.	%Hydrolysed.	pH.	%Hydrolysed.	pH.	%Hydrolysed.
0.0002N	6.84	0.061	7.04	0.1	6.04	0.08	7.24	0.16	7.12	0.12
0.0004	6.86	0.033	7.04	0.05	6.93	0.39	7.30	0.091	7.64	0.30
0.0006	7.34	0.007	7.52	0.10	7.48	0.092	7.74	0.17	8.10	0.38
0.0008	7.86	0.166	8.00	0.263	7.98	0.22	8.36	0.53	8.48	0.60
0.0010	8.56	0.670	8.70	0.91	8.46	0.53	8.84	1.26	8.77	1.04
0.1000	9.06	0.210	9.26	0.33	9.20	0.29	9.74	1.01	9.62	0.74

TABLE III

Solubilising power of the solutions of sodium salts of acids.

Mgm. of xylene/10 ml solution.

Conc.	Ethyl-	Butyl ⁿ -	Butyl ⁱ -	Butyl ^t -	Phenyl-
0.10N	249	312	277	236	361
0.05	172	275	241	214	335

DISCUSSION

The melting points of all the acids are less than those of the corresponding straight chain isomers. This may have been caused by the presence of the side chains which give rise to hindrance to compact fitting in the crystal lattice, resulting in the decrease of the melting point. More complex the substituent group, larger is the diminution of melting point from that of the straight chain isomer. This is evident from the melting points of the three butyl isomers recorded in Table I. Introduction of phenyl radical seems to work differently from the paraffinic side chains since diminution of the melting point of α -phenyl derivative from that of its straight chain isomer, arachidic, is only 2.3 units, whereas introduction of butyl^t reduces the melting point by 7 units from its isomer.

From the curves in Fig. 1 it is seen that like the straight chain isomer, α -substituted fatty acid salts in aqueous solution show a minima followed by a steep rise in % hydrolysis against concentration. This analogy tends to suggest that formation of acid soaps takes place during hydrolysis at lower concentrations.

FIG. 1

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to the α -ethyl, α -Buⁿ, α -Buⁱ, α -Bu^t, and phenyl Na-myristate.

FIG. 2

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to Na myristates as in Fig. 1.

The surface tension—concentration curves of the solutions of the sodium salts of the branched chain fatty acids show the typical behaviour of soaps (Fig. 2). The minima in the curve is at the concentration of 0.15% for α -ethylmyristate, 0.2%, 0.1%, and 0.15% for butylⁿ, butylⁱ and butyl^t myristates respectively. This evidently shows the effect of structure on the formation of ionic micelles. The critical micelle concentration for ethyl, butylⁿ, and butylⁱ are close to that of myristic acid salt which is a C₁₄ acid whereas ethyl and butyl derivatives are C₁₆ and C₁₈ acids respectively. Complexity of the substituted alkyl group further decreases the concentration as is found from the formation of critical micelle concentration of butyl^t derivative. The concentration needed is much less even than that of C₁₂ acid salt. The critical micelle concentration of the α -phenylmyristate, which is a salt of C₂₀ acid, lies near about that of the salt of C₁₆ acid. This indicates that substitution influences the substituted acids to behave like the lower members of the isomeric straight chain fatty acids. It may be ascribed to the higher solubility of the ionic micelles formed from the anions of the branched chain acids than that of the ionic micelles of the straight chain isomers.

Concentration required to decrease the surface tension to the lowest value for each of the three butyl- substituted myristates are different although their molecular weights are the same. Concentrations required are in the order: tert < iso < normal. This may be due to the fact that when these materials are dissolved in water, a definite number of molecules will be required to completely cover the surface of the solution in contact with the air. Molecules, when oriented with-COONa in water and hydrocarbon residue in the air, will occupy space according to their diameter. Since it is expected the diameters of the three acids will be in the order: tert > iso > normal, so the butyl^t derivative will require the least number of molecules to cover the same space.

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to the five Na myristates as in Fig. 1.

The critical micelle concentration observed in the surface tension/concentration curves is also confirmed by conductance measurement. The fall in conductance is fairly sharp at almost the same concentration where minima are observed in the surface tension/concentration curve. Turning towards solubilisation of hydrocarbon, such as xylene, it is found that as the number of carbon atoms in the chain increases, the solubilising power also increases.

It also depends on the nature of the chain. The above fact is quite in keeping with the mechanism of solubilisation which, it is said, is due to penetration of the solute into the intermicellar hydrophobic layers. It is more likely that the space occupied by the hydrocarbon residue of the branched chain acid is larger than that by the straight chain isomers. From the solubilising power of the three butyl isomers it is found that the longer the side chain, higher is the solubilising power. Sodium α -butylⁿ myristate has the highest solubilising power among the three isomers. It can be visualised that the shape of the micelle, whether it is lamellar or spheroidal, does not affect the considerations on which the solubilising power differs in the three isomeric butyl-substituted myristates.

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